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Language, LIC: Jarawara, ??

Date Completed:

Sources: 1. Dixon, R.M.W. "The eclectic morphology of Jarawara, and the status of word." in *Word: a Cross-Linguistic Typology*. Dixon, Aikhenvald, eds.

-highly synthetic, basically agglutinative (but developing fusion)

-some basic important info:

-closed class of 14 ADJ

-nouns take no prefixes, no distinctive suffixes (with a couple exceptions)

-verbs have 3 prefix slots for 6 possible prefixes, 24 suffix slots for at least 80 possible suffixes

-no grammatical elements are clitics

-generally, G- ω equals P- ω , except for 3 circumstances for 1 G- ω = 2 P- ω , and 1 circumstance for 1 P- ω = 2 G- ω (see below).

-Phonetic inventory:

-4 vowels: i, e, a, o (with contrastive length)

-11 consonants: b, Φ (written as *f*), m; t, n; s, r (with allophones [r] and [l]), \downarrow (written as *j*, with allophone [y]); k, w; \tilde{h} (written as *h*); and ? (written as ' , the glottal stop's occurrence is limited but significant and shall be discussed below).

-Syllable structure: (C)V

criteria for P- ω :

1. must include min. 2 moras (thus, monosyllabics have long V).

2. stress rule (see below) operates within P- ω .

3. phonological rules which relate to position in a word all apply within P- ω .

-pause possible at a position which is both P- ω and G- ω boundary

-Stress rule: based on penultimate mora: stress goes on syllables with the second, fourth, etc. mora from the end of the word (from the RIGHT).

'hosi 'sweet potato'

ko'baja 'white-collared peccary'

-rich set of ordered phonological rules, all applying just within verbs, for various types of assimilation, blending and elision, and morpheme realisation, some of which relate to the position of a syllable in a phonological word counting from the LEFT, for example:

RULE 8a: the initial -hV- is omitted from a tense-modal suffix [all tense-modal suffixes begin with a syllable -hV-] when (a) it is an even-numbered mora within a word, and (b) the preceding vowel is a.

ex:

ahaba + hara --> ahaba-ra (rule 8a applies)
be.finished IPef

tafa + hara --> tafa-hara (rule 8a doesn't apply)
eat IPef

-situations in which 1 G- ω consists of 2 P- ω (here, a colon represents a P- ω boundary within a G- ω , and not a long vowel):

1. compound nouns:

báni : *kasáko* 'wild dog species' (and not **baníkasáko*)

2. one type of verbal reduplication (in which the initial CVCV is repeated):

ketébe 'run, follow' which reduplicates as

kéte : *ketébe* 'run a lot' (and not **ketéketébe*)

3. most normal suffixes form one P- ω with what precedes and follows them in the same G- ω , but there are a [very] few normal suffixes for which the following is true:

if it is preceded by more than a single mora in the G- ω to which it belongs, then it begins a new P- ω within that G- ω . for example, the suffix -*tasa* 'again':

Okomobi ait o-mita : *tasa-habone* o-ke

name speech 1sA-listen.to : AGAIN-INTf 1s-DECf
I'll listen again to what Okomobi says (lit. to Okomobi's speech)

-and one situation in which 1 P- ω consists of 2 G- ω :

a non-inflecting verb root plus a following auxiliary *-na-* without an affix (here, a plus sign represents a G- ω boundary within a P- ω):

amó+na (the underlying form is ámo)

sleep+AUXaf

she sleeps

-every word ends in V, many begin with V, and a V#V sequence (where # is both G- ω and P- ω boundary) is unremarkable. However, if there is a vowel sequence across a P- ω boundary within a single G- ω , then a glottal stop is likely to be inserted between them:

mówe : ?éte 'fish species' (compound based on *mowe* and *ete*)

áta : ?atábo 'be very muddy' (reduplication based on *atábo* 'be muddy')

-there is a category of verb suffixes which are auxiliary bound; they cannot be added directly to a verb, but require their own "suffix-determined auxiliary (AUXd)". One example is *-wahare/-wahari* 'do many times in many places'; however, it is more appropriate to analyze this as *-wahar/* because the allophone variations of // (namely [e] and [i]) are determined by a phonological rule based on moras of a P- ω as counted from the left: // is realized as [e] when it is an even-number mora, and as [i] when comprising an odd-numbered mora.

Okomobi tafa na-wahare-hare-ka (would be [wahari] if what precedes it were 1 mora longer)

name eat AUXd-MULTIPLE-IPem-DECm

Okomobi ate in many houses